

Assessing Content-Based Instruction (CBI) in the Context of Teaching English at the Tertiary Level of Bangladesh

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Abstract: *This study aims to assess the English language outcome of Content-Based Instruction (CBI) among EFL learners of English at the tertiary level of Bangladesh and the problems involved in this process, where a group of students and teachers (existing) of English department were the focus of the study. To conduct this study, a mixed-method approach was applied where research instruments such as questionnaire and classroom observation were used. In total, 279 (students=260, teachers=19) respondents participated in the survey questionnaires and classroom observations. The findings of this study suggested that though teachers and students prefer the CBI approach, some drawbacks were found in this learning process.*

Keywords: *Content-Based Instruction, Tertiary Level Learners of Bangladesh, EFL context*

Introduction

English language teaching has been the most challenging tasks in Bangladeshi EFL (English as a Foreign Language) context. Around half of the world's population speak in more than one language and therefore, learning a foreign language has now become necessity (Richards & Rodgers, 2001, p. 3). There are several teaching methods found all around the world to teach English to foreign language learners. However, the mode of instruction in case of teaching English at the tertiary level of Bangladesh is Content-Based Instruction (CBI).

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The education system in Bangladesh is moving towards a transition from just learning content to learning language.

CBI is not a new idea; it is rather the most used teaching technique in the EFL context of Bangladesh, especially at the tertiary setting. The students are supposed to be more skilled in implementing English after completing their graduation, however, in most cases, this does not happen. One of the reasons behind this is to put less emphasis on acquiring language skills. Another major factor is that English language skills in Bangladesh are evaluated mostly on written test, not on practical uses of English, and instead of learning language, achieving a good score in examination becomes a primary concern for learners (Tahereen, 2014). Consequently, students are found memorizing content rather than being able to use the English language independently for communicative intents. Tertiary level learners of English, thus, should know the applied uses of language while learning across varying content to have a beneficial effect of CBI approach.

The primary aim of this study is to explore the impact of CBI on the students' English language learning, and in doing so, three research questions have been specified-

1. What are the teachers' views about CBI while teaching English at the tertiary level?
2. Is it possible for the Bangladeshi EFL students to develop their language learning skills through CBI approach?
3. What are the problems usually faced by the students and teachers while implementing CBI in the English classroom?

2. Literature Review

2.1 Content-Based Instruction (CBI)

Content-Based Instruction is a second/foreign language teaching method where the language is taught through the content of the syllabus. Content-Based Instruction (CBI) is a teaching approach which emphasizes the learners mastering both language and content (Stoller, 2002). In this case, the focus is not on the language alone but on the subject matter which will be

taught by using the target language (Richards & Rodgers, 2001). As the classroom activities of CBI revolve around the subject matter, it enhances students' thinking and learning through the target language which ultimately integrates the reading, writing, speaking and listening skills (Grabe & Stoller, 1997).

In this approach, learners are found communicating socially to get the meaning (Stern 1992, p.302) and it is the content that chooses the language skills to be taught without incorporating any individual language course in the teaching process (Brinton, 2003). Authenticity is one of the key elements of the CBI approach, where an authentic text and task should mirror those activities which eventually would take place in real-world situations (Brinton, 2003). Shang (2006) says that class activities in case of CBI in the EFL literature curriculum should focus on learning content, involving in critical thinking, and enhancing English language skills. Moreover, the literary text provides valuable authentic material for learners, increases ideas about cultural context, enriches language by engaging them into learning method (Collie & Slater, 1987).

2.2 Related Literature in case of Teaching English through CBI

Beatrice C. Dupuy (2000) found that CBI helped all levels of students by increasing foreign language competency, subject matter knowledge, and self-confidence. Amiri and Fatemi (2014) noted that this approach was more effective than the Grammar Translation Method (GTM) as learners might be able to get better scores if they collaborate in group learning. CBI approach facilitated students to enhance their English reading comprehension (Khruawan & Dennis, 2017).

Jiaying Howard (2006) concluded that maintaining balance between language and content or subject matter could improve students' language learning process as these topics were related to their academic goals. As CBI reflects on students' academic goals, their interests and needs, it provides meaningful content for students to acquire English language skills (Villalobos, 2013) and students get the chance of using their language skills when different activities are integrated into the classroom (Tseng, 2015). However, Lai and Aksornjarung (2018) in their research work showed that students seemed to

possess confusion regarding CBI approach that they were not fully convinced of the dual objectives of mastering both content and language. Michael C. Cheng, Chang Jui-Chuan, Chen Yi-Chen, and Liao Ying-shu (2010) reported that students preferred more language skill training courses than the content-driven sheltered approach and the language-driven thematic approach. While speaking about the strengths and weaknesses of CBI, Zubeyde Sinem Yildiz-Genc (2011) observed that students were much more efficient in their grammar, vocabulary and reading skills in comparison to their speaking, listening and writing skills in English and proposed to develop the less competent skills by practising more authentic activities out of the class.

3. Research Methodology

The research method in this study is a mixed-method approach. The researchers randomly chose 5 institutions from Cumilla district, Bangladesh, (one public university, three private universities, and one national university) to become a representative sample of the entire population. To do this, the researchers applied Cluster Random Sampling Method. The primary data were collected between 6 January to 24 January 2021.

3.1 Sampling Area

Due to the economical constraints and time limitations, the researchers restricted the sampling area to the Cumilla district, Bangladesh and visited five universities from five different areas of Cumilla, and they are- Comilla University, Bangladesh Army International University of Science and Technology, CCN University of Science and Technology, Britannia University, and Sonar Bangla College (National University).

3.2 Sampling Population

The researchers' target population was students (2nd year, 3rd year, 4th year and master's) and teachers (present) from the English department. The total sample population is two hundred and seventy-nine (279). The distribution of sampling population according to the sampling area is shown in the following table-

Table 1: Distribution of sampling population according to the sampling area

Sampling area	Sampling population
Comilla University	Students=179 Teachers=8
Britannia University	Students=35 Teachers=3
Bangladesh Army International University of Science and Technology	Students=22 Teachers=4
CCN University of Science and Technology	Students=4 Teacher=1
Sonar Bangla College (National University)	Students=20 Teacher=3
Total=	279

3.3 Research Instruments

Since the nature of the study is the mixed-method approach, the researchers adopted two research instruments-

i) Questionnaires

For quantitative data, the researchers chose a five-point (1-5) Likert-type scale questionnaire and prepared two separate questionnaires - one for the teachers and another for the students. Both the questionnaires were divided into 4 sections because the researchers' concentration was to find out the students' attitude towards CBI approach, teachers' and students' performances, as well as how CBI is dealt in the classroom to explore the language outcome of the CBI method.

Students' questionnaire consists of 18 statements-

Table 2: Distribution of statements (students' questionnaire)

No.	Sections	Statements
1	Content-Based Instruction (CBI) in the English classroom	1-3
2	Syllabus	4-7
3	Classroom Activities	8-12
4	Students' improvement in English language skills	13-18

Teachers' questionnaire consists of 16 statements-

Table 3: Distribution of statements (teachers' questionnaire)

No.	Sections	Statements
1	Content-Based Instruction (CBI) in the English classroom	1-3
2	Syllabus	4-7
3	Classroom Activities	8-10
4	Students' improvement in English language skills	11-16

ii) Classroom Observations

After collecting data through questionnaires, the researchers as non-participant observers attended classes to see if the questionnaire data matches with those observations. The observation method was a structured one, as the researchers prepared a classroom observation checklist to ensure the units to be observed.

The researchers specified some criteria in the checklist and assigned them to the scale given-

1. Observed 2. Could Improve 3. Not Observed

In Total, 9 classes were observed of 9 teachers. Also, the researchers took some notes and wrote comments regarding the classes which were found very beneficial for the study.

3.4 Data Analysis Tool

The researchers opted for MS Excel-2016, and Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 20 for analyzing data through 'Descriptive Statistics' to bring out the average responses given by both teachers and students, in the form of percentage and mean score, where mean score 1 to 2.50 indicate to the side of the agreement, and 2.51 to 5.00 to the side of the disagreement.

3.5 Ethical Consideration

The researchers were very careful regarding the confidentiality of the respondents and assured them that their identities will never be disclosed to anybody following the privacy policy.

4. Findings and Analysis

As mentioned above, both students' and teachers' data were collected through a five-point (1-5) Likert-type scale questionnaire from five different institutions. Findings and analysis of these data are illustrated under four sections (see table 2,3)-

4.1 Findings and analysis of students' questionnaire-

4.1.1 Content-Based Instruction (CBI) in the English Classroom

Majority students (74.2%) agreed that CBI helped them to gain more workable knowledge of the language than the traditional language learning method, but at the same time, a surprising number of students (83.9%) said CBI required a lot of effort to learn different items such as poem, drama, novel, etc. (see appendix-1, statement-1,2).

4.1.2 Syllabus

Students (58.4%) commented that syllabus focuses equally on all the four language skills (reading, writing, speaking, listening), while, only one fourth (25.4%) of them disagreed (see appendix-1 statement-4). In the questionnaire, students were presented with the statement "The scope of learning a language in a CBI syllabus is quite narrow", surprisingly, 71.9% students agreed, as opposed to their response where they (62.7%) responded that CBI is an effective way of learning language (see appendix-1 statement-3,6). A dominant group of students (83.1%) agreed with the point that syllabus should not only contain content, but it must also have a language outcome (see appendix-1 statement-7).

4.1.3 Classroom Activities

More than half of the students (63.8%) agreed that they were involved in interactive learning (see appendix-1 statement-8). In response to the statement no.11 (see appendix-1), about three fourth of the students (71.9%) believed that assignments on a particular topic motivated them to acquire English language skills. Another statement was used to know if presentations

motivated them to acquire English language skills, the majority of the students (85%) responded positively (see appendix-1 statement-12).

4.1.4 Students' Improvement of English Language Skills

An extensive number of students approved that CBI has indeed developed their reading (89.3%), writing (85%) and vocabulary (87.7%) skills, where, a moderate number of them rated it has increased their listening (58.1%), speaking (67.3%) and grammatical (56.9%) skills. (see appendix-1 statement-13,14,15,16,17,18).

4.2 Findings and analysis of teachers' questionnaire-

4.2.1 Content-Based Instruction (CBI) in the English Classroom

Without any doubt, teachers (100%) agreed that CBI helped students to gain more workable knowledge of the language, and they (89.5%) found CBI an effective way of teaching English in Bangladeshi EFL classroom. Like students, teachers (94.8%) also strongly opined that CBI requires a lot of effort to teach different items. (see appendix-2 statement-1,2,3)

4.2.2 Syllabus

In replying the statement "Syllabus focuses equally on all the four language skills of English (reading, writing, speaking, listening)", 33.3% teachers agreed. Surprisingly, half of them (50%) did not think the same way (see appendix-2 statement-4). Almost all teachers (94.8%) stated that syllabus should not only contain content, but it must also have a language outcome (see appendix-2 statement-6). Majority teachers (89.4%) also opined that students are still weak in English because there is not enough language focus in the syllabus (see appendix-2 statement-7).

4.2.3 Classroom Activities

A considerable number of teachers (73.7%) said that they engaged students in interactive learning, such as- debates, discussions, role-plays, peer works, etc. According to the teachers, assignments (89.4%) and presentations (100%)

surely motivated students to acquire language skills. (see appendix-2 statement-8,9,10)

4.2.4 Students' Improvement of English Language Skills

Teachers also believed that students' reading (84.2%), writing (78.9%) and vocabulary (84.2%) skills could be developed in the CBI approach. Although majority teachers (68.5%) noted that CBI has improved students' grammar skills, not a very significant number of them agreed it has increased their speaking (63.2%) and listening (57.9%) skills in comparison to reading, writing and vocabulary skills. (see appendix-2 statement-11,12,13,14,15,16)

4.3 Findings and Analysis of Classroom Observations

The teachers whose classes were observed provided the researchers insight into the classroom activities, teachers' and students' attitude towards the CBI teaching-learning method. Findings and analysis from these classroom observations are discussed as below-

Classroom Observation 1-

The researchers, in the first observation, found the teacher speaking in English while giving a lecture, but he was not encouraging students to give their opinion. Students were communicating in Bangla while speaking with their teacher or their peers regarding the topic. Class size and duration was enough to do different interactive activities, but the researchers could see no such activity in the class. The researchers observed that students were feeling bored during the long class.

Classroom Observation 2-

In this class too, the teacher was giving a lecture in English. He was dealing with the post-colonial literature *The Shadow Line* by Amitav Ghosh. Though there was enough teacher-student interaction in the class as he was asking students to give their opinion, students were not engaged into collaborative work and they were somewhat dependent on the teacher for all sources of information. Students were found somewhat bored and tired by the end of the class.

Classroom Observation 3-

The researchers noticed that the student's communication ability was given more importance in this class which was on the poem "Good and Evil" by Khalil Gibran. The teacher gave the students a task- to find out some binary opposition words, which obviously could improve their reading and vocabulary skills in English. But students were not speaking in English except their class teacher. Though some of the students had a positive attitude towards what the teacher was dealing with, still, a few did not respond during the long class.

Classroom Observation 4-

In this second-year class, the researchers could observe a quiz test conducted by the teacher. The teacher also gave a reading task which involved students to find some new vocabulary from the text. Students got a chance of evaluating themselves during the task, but not their peers. The teacher used the English language while delivering lectures and also students' communication ability was given some importance in the class.

Classroom Observation 5-

During this class, the researchers could see that students were very much involved in interacting with their teacher. Students were also seen taking notes and writing comments as the lecture was very informative. By the end of the class, the teacher gave them a written assignment and presentation. But there were no student-centred and language-related activities found in the class.

Classroom Observation 6-

The teacher started the class about alternative assessment and asked them to write down some ways of alternative assessment. Throughout the class, the researchers observed students' participation more than the teacher. Because the teacher was not only focusing on the content but also engaging them in different activities. Finally, he gave them a written assignment on the same topic and encouraged them to try out more creative ideas.

Classroom Observation 7-

The next class observed was on the 'Communicative Language Teaching' approach. The teacher involved students in a pair work and asked them to write down some advantages and disadvantages of CLT approach. After they had finished their writing, the teacher allowed them to share their writing with their peers to evaluate and get feedback. Both teachers and students were seen speaking in Bangla during the class.

Classroom Observation 8-

In the next class, students were following their teacher's instruction while writing down the format of 'lesson plan'. The teacher was seen speaking in English and responding to any questions asked by the students and also gave them a task to prepare a lesson plan by themselves. Again, there was not enough activities which would help students increase their language skills.

Classroom Observation 9-

The researchers observed teacher-student interaction in the next class, as the researchers saw there was a question-answer session by the end of the class. The teacher assigned them a presentation for the next class. Though the researchers could see no skill-based activity occurred during the class, the presentation task sure was an effective way of developing their speaking in the English language.

5. Discussion

The results are discussed from three perspectives-teachers' questionnaire, students' questionnaire and classroom observations, and also by relating the views of previous works done on Content-Based Instruction (CBI). The comparison between teachers' and students' responses were also evaluated where mean score 1 to 2.50 indicate to the side of the agreement, while 2.51-5 to the side of the disagreement. Most importantly, the three research questions are answered considering the findings from the survey questionnaires and classroom observations.

5.1 Content-Based Instruction (CBI) in the English Classroom

The statistical analysis showed that CBI lends students to acquire the English language more effectively and practically than the traditional language learning method and it is also approved by all teachers (see figure-1,2), which indicates that students have a very positive attitude towards CBI. This finding agrees with the result of a study conducted by Lai and Aksornjarung (2018), suggesting that students tended to prefer CBI teaching.

However, students in English at the tertiary level of Bangladesh deal with a variety of contents like poems, dramas, novels, linguistics, etc., that is why majority students responded, it takes a lot of effort to learn a variety of contents from their part and teachers also believe CBI indeed involves laborious work to teach those items (see figure-1,2). The first three classes the researchers have observed (see classroom observations 1,2,3), found students to be very indifferent and bored towards the class and the content to what the teachers were giving lectures on. According to teachers, literature is a useful mode of teaching English (see figure-1), because it eliminates students' fear of English language, and speaking/sharing information about literary themes and ideas enhances language learning (Shang, 2006). Majority students also hold the same opinion in terms of seeing literature as a feasible mode of learning the English language, still, this point of view is different according to some of them (see figure-1). One of the most important findings of this study is that, though teachers think CBI helps students to learn the language, students are not exposed enough to language learning process and almost all the classrooms observed (see classroom observations 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 8, 9) by the researchers also proved this view.

Figure-1: Comparative Evaluation of “CBI in the English Classroom”

Figure-2: Overall mean score of “CBI in the English Classroom”

5.2 Syllabus

The results showed that although slightly over half of the students claimed CBI syllabus focused equally on all the four language skills (reading, writing, speaking, listening), surprisingly enough, half of the teachers think that CBI syllabus is not focusing on major language skills equally (see figure-4). Moreover, the observed classes showed that teacher could engage the students in various language activities.

Every syllabus is designed to have some outcomes, be it knowledge of the language or the understanding of content. Therefore, both teachers and students opined that syllabus must have a language outcome rather than

focusing only on the content. (see figure-4,5).

Despite this, students thought that the opportunity to learn the language in CBI syllabus is limited (see appendix-1 statement-6), because there is not balance between language and literature items in the syllabus (see figure-4,5). Accordingly, this situation led teachers to think that their students are not still skilled in English because language skills are underestimated in CBI syllabus (see figure-3).

Figure 3: Teachers' perspectives on language focus

Shang (2006) noted that students of EFL background find it hard to figure out academic contents as these are not written in their mother tongue, and this happens when learners did not have any opportunity to engage more with the language learning skills, and therefore, they are found confused during their whole learning process.

Figure-4: Comparative Evaluation of “Syllabus”

Figure-5: Overall mean score of “Syllabus”

Classroom Activities

There is a whole range of activities that an English classroom can arrange, and these activities can help students to learn language through content. Tseng (2015) in a study proved that the employment of cooperative learning, such as, group tasks help alleviate students’ anxiety and uncertainty when they can negotiate the content and language problems with their peers in the group. This is also supported by Stern (1992), who said that in task-based language

learning, students get the chance of experimenting their knowledge related to projects or problems which they face in their day-to-day life. The students and teachers, surveyed, also responded positively that learners are involved in such kind of interactive learning like discussions role plays, peer works, etc., but not all seem to have the same opinion (see figure - 6, 7). Though, the researchers observed in some classes that the teachers engage students into communicative learning (see classroom observation - 6, 7), these activities were not practised in most classes, as the teachers were focusing mainly on teaching content rather than the language.

It is found from students' survey that they are not much interested in the written assignment (see appendix-1 statement - 9), because in most cases they are given one single topic on which everyone has to perform. Therefore, writing assignments become just a formality rather than developing skill. However, this finding contradicts with the result (see appendix - 1 statement - 11) where majority students rated that assignment on a particular topic motivates them to acquire English language skill; it seems that students are a little bit confused regarding their performance in an assignment.

Presentations, being an activity to present and interact with the audience, are found more interesting and innovative than an assignment by the majority of the students (see appendix - 1 statement 10). English teachers see presentations, and unlike students, consider assignments to be a motivational factor for students to learn the language (see figure - 6). This is in line with one of the rationales provided by Grabe and Stoller (1997), where they indicated that in CBI classroom, students negotiate with content through language in natural discourse contexts. However, comparing the responses found regarding presentations and assignment, it is evident that presentations motivate to acquire English language skills more than the assignments (see figure-7).

Figure-6: Comparative Evaluation of “Classroom Activities”

Figure-7: Overall mean score of “Classroom Activities”

5.3 Students’ Improvement of English Language Skills

Barman, Sultana and Basu (2006) indicated that CBI offers some opportunity for students in which they can increase their proficiency in the foreign language by studying a particular content or subject. Findings of this statistical analysis also presented a picture of students’ language ability, that is, how much of language students have acquired through learning content in CBI approach. Comparing the result found from both teachers’ and students’ perspective, some opinions can be drawn.

Lai and Aksornjarung (2018) reported that CBI course has improved their English speaking and listening. But in the present study, it is found that students seem to have more expertise in reading and writing skills, in comparison to their speaking and listening skills (see figure - 8). This is because, in CBI syllabus and classroom tasks, more focus is given on reading books and writing contents in exams. Therefore, students lack the motivation to increase their speaking and listening skills compared to reading and writing skills. Teachers also hold similar perception where they agreed that CBI has developed students' reading and writing skills, but they don't see students' speaking and listening as good as reading and writing skills (see figure - 8). The observed classes also proved this view (see classroom observation - 1, 3, 4, 5, 7).

In CBI context, students are mostly benefited in terms of their vocabulary skill, which can be interpreted by students' and teachers' responses (see figure - 8) found from the study, as well as some observations where the researchers noticed vocabulary related tasks (see classroom observations 3, & 4).

Grammar in CBI context is sometimes underestimated than the other skills, though around half of the students responded positively that CBI approach has developed their grammatical skills, some of them don't see any improvement (see appendix – 1, statement-17). The researchers in the observed classes did not see any tasks that would develop students' grammatical skills. A study by Mamun (2015) found that in case of EFL context it is essential to learn grammar. If grammatical accuracy is taken into consideration with much importance, then it might help students to perform their language skills without any error.

Figure-8: Comparative evaluation of “Students’ Improvement of English Language Skills”

Research question 1- Research question one concerned teachers’ views about CBI while teaching English at the tertiary level of Bangladesh, and most of them viewed that language competency must be given as much importance as teaching content.

Research question 2- Research question two considered language outcome of students, which showed that students have developed their language skills through Content-Based Instruction, but there is much room for improvement.

Research question 3- Research question three found that there exist some problems while implementing CBI in English classroom, such as- CBI approach involves huge contents which take a lot of endeavours to complete entire syllabus within the academic session, as a consequence, students feel stressed during this lengthy learning process. Another problem regarding CBI approach is that in the tertiary setting literature items are given more importance than the language skills, which is a clear evidence of students’

poor performance in English language skills. Students are not always involved in interactive as well as negotiation and information gathering learning (language-based), because the classroom activities limit students' participation in the class. Despite having learned English since their secondary level, Bangladeshi tertiary level learners still are not fully and equally efficient in reading, writing, listening and speaking skills of English.

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study has provided insight into Content-Based Instruction (CBI) in teaching English at the tertiary level of Bangladesh by assessing CBI approach from three different perspectives (teachers, students, and classroom observations). Richards and Rodgers (2001, p. 205) implied that if students were introduced with real-life situations in this method, they will then automatically acquire language. As it is found from the results, both language acquisition and learning content should be given equal importance in CBI approach. By implementing a whole range of interactive activities in the CBI classroom from the role-play to oral presentation, students are provided with chances to use the language in a meaningful context (Tseng, 2015). Although students agreed that CBI has indeed developed their English language skills, there still remains some questions regarding- how much of language they have acquired through this approach to communicate in a real-world context. Therefore-

- The contents included in the CBI syllabus must be chosen considering students' needs so that they become more interested in learning language through content.
- Both teachers and students recommended that syllabus should not only contain content, but it must also have a language outcome at the end of the academic year.
- Interactive learning (regarding the topic or theme of a novel, play, poem) should be introduced more and more in CBI classes.
- It is found from teachers' responses that they emphasize more on the content than the language. But, if they want students to communicate in English in a meaningful way, they should engage students in language-based activities depending on the topic of a novel, play, poem, etc.
- Getting feedback on a performance develops a positive attitude among

students, therefore, this should be practised more by the teachers.

- Students should try to evaluate their learning of content and language as this creates awareness among them about their weaknesses.

From the survey questionnaires, it is revealed that students are still troubled by the long, boring learning process of CBI because of the huge contents included in the CBI syllabus which they must complete by the allotted time of their academic session. Also, CBI syllabus does not put equal emphasis on reading, writing, speaking, listening. Consequently, a lack of skill can be found in their speaking and listening rather than their reading and writing ability. They don't get much opportunity to practice these skills individually. Therefore, CBI classes should involve activities that combine those skills, because this is how learners communicate socially (Richards and Rodgers, 2001, p.208). Students memorize contents and memorization in the EFL context kills students' critical thinking. For purposeful communication regarding the contents to occur, students must have practical competence in English language skills rather than just memorizing contents. Students also discover the gaps existing in their learning process when they are allowed to evaluate their learning outcome, in terms of both content and language. If implemented appropriately, CBI will surely have a greater impact on students' English language learning process besides being just competent in learning content. However, this research paper has some limitations. This research paper failed to address to what extent language skills are learnt by the students. The result of the study may not be generalized as the sampling population belonged to the southeastern region of Bangladesh.

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Appendix-1**Findings and analysis of students' questionnaire**

(SA=Strongly Agree, A=Agree, N= Neutral, D=Disagree, SD=Strongly Disagree)

No	Statements	Responses (%)					Mean score
		SA	A	N	D	SD	
1	CBI helps you to gain more workable knowledge of the language than the traditional language learning method.	23.8	50.4	15.0	9.6	1.2	2.14
2	CBI requires a lot of effort to learn different items (poem, drama, novel, etc.).	42.7	41.2	10.4	4.2	1.5	1.81
3	Literature as Content-Based Instruction is an effective way of learning language.	26.5	36.2	19.6	12.3	5.4	2.34
4	Syllabus focuses equally on all the four language skills (reading, writing, speaking, listening).	29.6	28.8	16.2	21.2	4.2	2.42
5	There is a balance between language and literature items in the syllabus.	23.1	29.2	20.4	21.2	6.2	2.58
6	The scope of learning language in CBI syllabus is quite narrow.	34.2	37.7	10.0	15.0	3.1	2.15
7	Syllabus should not only contain content, but it must also have a language outcome.	38.5	44.6	13.1	3.5	.4	1.83
8	You are involved in interactive learning (debates, discussions, role plays, peer works and authentic tasks, etc.).	14.2	49.6	21.2	12.3	2.7	2.40
9	Assignments in Content-Based Instruction are interesting to complete.	18.1	29.6	23.8	20.4	8.1	2.71
10	Presentations in Content-Based Instruction are enjoyable to perform.	18.8	36.5	22.7	16.9	5.0	2.53

11	Assignments on a particular topic motivate you to acquire English language skills.	36.9	35.0	10.4	12.7	5.0	2.14
12	Presentation on a particular topic motivate you to acquire English language skills.	39.6	45.4	6.9	5.0	3.1	1.87
13	CBI has developed your English reading skill.	45.8	43.5	5.8	4.2	.8	1.71
14	CBI has developed your English writing skill.	39.6	45.4	8.1	6.5	.4	1.83
15	CBI has developed your English listening skill.	21.2	36.9	17.3	18.5	6.2	2.52
16	CBI has developed your English-speaking skill.	24.2	43.1	15.0	14.6	3.1	2.29
17	CBI has developed your English grammar skill.	17.3	39.6	21.2	16.9	5.0	2.53
18	CBI has developed your English vocabulary skill.	35.8	51.9	8.5	3.1	.8	1.81

Appendix-2

Findings and analysis of teachers' questionnaire

(SA=Strongly Agree, A=Agree, N= Neutral, D=Disagree, SD=Strongly Disagree)

No.	Statements	Responses (%)					Mean score
		SA	A	N	D	SD	
1	CBI helps students to gain more workable knowledge of the language than the traditional language teaching method.	31.6	68.4	0	0	0	1.68
2	Literature as Content-Based Instruction is an effective way of teaching language.	26.3	63.2	0	10.5	0	1.95
3	CBI requires a lot of effort to teach different items (poems, novels, plays, etc.).	21.1	73.7	5.3	0	0	1.84

4	Syllabus focuses equally on all the four language skills of English (reading, writing, speaking, listening).	11.1	22.2	16.7	38.9	11.1	3.17
5	There is a balance between language and literature items in the syllabus.	5.6	38.9	16.7	33.3	5.6	2.94
6	Syllabus should not only contain content, but it must also have a language outcome.	63.2	31.6	5.3	0	0	1.42
7	Students are still weak in English because there is not enough language focus in the syllabus.	36.8	52.6	10.5	0	0	1.74
8	You engage students into interactive learning (debates, discussions, role plays, peer works).	0	73.7	15.8	5.3	5.3	2.42
9	Assignment on a particular topic motivates students to acquire language.	10.5	78.9	5.3	5.3	0	2.05
10	Presentation on a particular topic motivates students to acquire language.	36.8	63.2	0	0	0	1.63
11	CBI has developed students' reading skill.	31.6	52.6	10.5	5.3	0	1.89
12	CBI has developed students' writing skill.	36.8	42.1	15.8	5.3	0	1.89
13	CBI has developed students' speaking skill.	5.3	57.9	15.8	21.1	0	2.53
14	CBI has developed students' listening skill.	5.3	52.6	15.8	26.3	0	2.63
15	CBI has developed students' vocabulary skill.	15.8	68.4	15.8	0	0	2.00
16	CBI has developed students' grammar skill.	5.3	63.2	21.1	10.5	0	2.37

Appendix-3
Classroom Observation Checklist

Teacher’s name:

Level of the students:

Topic of the class:

Class duration:

Time:

Department:

Institute:

Date:

No.	Statements	Observed	Could Improve	Not Observed
1	Teacher emphasizes more on the content than the language.			
2	There is enough teacher-student interaction in the class.			
3	There are enough student-centered classroom activities.			
4	Students’ communication ability is given more importance in the class.			
5	Teaching process focuses on the reading skill.			
6	Teaching process focuses on the writing skill.			
7	Teaching process focuses on the speaking skill.			
8	Teaching process focuses on the listening skill.			
9	Students feel bored and tired during the class.			
10	Students are engaged into different interactive activities.			
11	Teacher speaks in English while giving lecture.			

Comments:.....

